

Acceptance Letter

This certify that the paper „Problems of Mycotic Keratitis – An epidemiological study“ presented by Dr. Nehal S. Shehab (Public Health Department) & Dr. Mohamed Sameh ElShorbagy (Ophthalmology Department, who are the speakers and Dr. Anwer Elbadry (Microbiology & Mycology Department), was accepted in the Tropical Ophthalmology Meeting, held in Munich - Germany, in the period of 16th – 20th October 2000 and is ready to be published.

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Problems of Mycotic Keratitis: An Epidemiological Study

By

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Abstract

Purpose: The object of this work is to study the problems encountered and the different epidemiological features of patients with fungal keratitis.

Subjects and Methods: All cases with keratitis attending the Outpatient Clinic of Ophthalmology Department of Tanta University during the summer months from the first of May to the end of August of the year 2000 were selected and carefully examined and cases with mycotic keratitis were further examined and investigated.

Results: Out of a total 8030 attendants during this period with different complaints, there were 50 cases (0.62 %) with mycotic keratitis and 75 cases (0.93 %) of non-mycotic origin that is the control group. Results revealed that mycotic keratitis is common in age group between 40 – 60 years , more in : * farmers (64 %) , * families with large number and large crowding index , * rural than urban residents , * patients with outdoor water sources and insanitary sewage disposal. Laboratory findings were positive in 80 % for fungal growth and negative in 20 % of cases in spite of their typical clinical findings for diagnosis and their improvement with antifungal therapy.

Conclusion: Mycotic keratitis is most frequent in farmers, rural areas, in outdoor water supply , insanitary sewage disposal , patients preceded with organic trauma. Not all laboratory findings were positive , not all the cases have the typical findings for clinical diagnosis and not all the cases improved with anti fungal therapy even after culture and sensitivity.

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Introduction:

Mycotic keratitis is a severe problem in most of the developing countries; where as specific antifungal agents are expensive and commercially unavailable as ready compounds for topical ocular use. Besides, its endemicity is favoured by certain ecological factors already exist in those communities⁽¹⁾. Other problems included, difficulties in its clinical diagnosis, laboratory results and treatment⁽¹⁾.

Mycotic keratitis is an important cause of corneal morbidity, scarring and blindness caused by fungal invasion through corneal epithelium⁽²⁾. The disease was found to be more common among agricultural communities than others⁽³⁾.

According to predisposing factors, clinical features and response to treatment, fungal corneal pathogens were divided into : filamentous fungi, yeast, yeast like and dimorphic fungi⁽⁴⁾. The most common filamentous fungi causing keratomycosis are Aspergillus, Fusarium, Curvularia, Alternaria and Cladosporium, while Candida albicans is the commonest form of yeasts⁽⁵⁾.

Mycotic keratitis probably arises as a result of an interaction between different agent factors as invasiveness & toxigenicity of fungal strains and host factors due to local or systemic causes⁽⁶⁾. The invasiveness of fungal strains is aided by certain properties such as the capacity of fungus to adhere to the cells and to produce enzymes and toxins that destroy anatomical defenses⁽⁷⁾.

Fungi specially filamentous species rarely infect healthy cornea spontaneously and usually predisposed by trauma with vegetable or organic matter. On the other hand candida albicans is a common infection in compromised or immunosuppressed cornea⁽⁸⁾.

Identification of pathogenic corneal fungi is performed either by microscopic stained corneal scrapes or by their cultural features⁽⁹⁾.

Other methods for fungus identification depend on the types of enzymes produced, immunodiffusion, electrophoresis and ELISA⁽¹⁰⁾.

The three major groups of antifungal agents are⁽¹¹⁾ :

A-Polyenes: as Amphotericin B and Nystatin.

B-Azoles : as Itraconazole and Fluconazole

C-Pyrimidines: as Flucytosine

Aim of the work:

The aim of this work is to study the epidemiologic features of mycotic keratitis, factors affecting their prevalence and the difficulties encountered with such type of corneal affection either in diagnosis laboratory findings or treatment.

Patients and Methods:

The study was conducted during summer months from the first of May to the end of August, 2000; at the Outpatient Clinic of Tanta University Ophthalmology Hospital.

A total number of 8030 patients with different ophthalmological complaints were examined during that period. All patients with corneal lesions were selected and carefully examined.

Our target included those cases diagnosed clinically as fungal keratitis, they were 50 cases during that period. Clinical diagnosis of mycotic keratitis was dependent on some clinical criteria ^{(12) & (13)} including:

- * Thick area of keratitis
- * Thick hypopyon "coagulum" , with or without level
- * Immune rings
- * Satellite lesions
- * Stromal infiltrate with feathery edge
- * Healing usually with dense leucoma with large solitary BV.
- * Area of epithelial defect is usually smaller than stromal infiltration.

A control group included all cases of non mycotic keratitis attended the clinic during the same period, they were 75 cases of both bacterial and viral origin.

All cases of mycotic and non mycotic keratitis were submitted to a complete ophthalmological examination, including direct torch examination, slit lamp examination using direct oblique , scleral scatter, and retroillumination techniques. Corneal staining with fluorescein and rose bengal was done.

A questionnaire sheet was designed and filled by the researchers for cases and control including:

A- Biologic and Socio-demographic data: - age, sex, occupation, family size, crowding index (family members/` number of rooms), residence , source of water whether indoor or outdoor, sewage disposal whether pipes system or conservancy system.

B- History taking for: - some risk factors such as recent drug intake (prolonged antibiotics and local or systemic corticosteroids) ; corneal Trauma whether organic or non organic; systemic diseases (D.M., TB, cancer,..); ocular surgery; local eye diseases such as glaucoma and the time of onset of complaints till examination.

C- Laboratory investigations: -all cases diagnosed clinically as fungal keratitis were submitted to:

* **Sampling:** Under surface anaesthesia ,the active edge and the bed of ulcer were scraped using platinum spatula or sterile surgical blade (No.15) with the aid of slit lamp biomicroscopy or surgical microscope to ensure that adequate corneal material was obtained and to avoid corneal perforation.

Some ulcers were very soft ,sticky and mucoid in consistency, so disposable calcium alginate cotton tipped sterile applicators were used for those cases.

- **Isolation media:** Sabouraud's glucose agar was prepared with 0.05 % chloramphenicol , autoclaved ,spread on sterile Perti plates. Plates were incubated at room temperature, fungal growth was identified then sensitivity tests were carried out in vitro by using these available antifungal agents shown in table (1).

Table (1) Antifungal agents used in sensitivity tests

Trade name	Scientific name	Concentration
Diflucan(Pfizer comp.)	Fluconazole	2mg/ml
Fungizone (Squibb comp.)	Amphotericin B	2.5 mg/ml
Sporonox(Jans sen-Cilag)	Itraconazole	10 mg/ml

- * Patients with mycotic keratitis and plates of isolated fungi are shown in figure (1).
- * According to the results of sensitivity tests , the appropriate antifungal agent shown in table 1 prepared for topical use were started as one drop hourly during the waking hours up to 5 days. Once healing was observed (a decrease in ulcer size or reepithelization and improvement of patient's complaints) ,the dose was reduced to 3 times daily for 2 weeks.

The treatment regimen used for all cases was:

- * Amphotericin B (2mg/ml) topically till the results of culture appear.
- * For non-filamentous fungi specially Candida we continue with Amphotericin B
- * For filamentous fungi , we stop Amphotericin B and replaced by topical Itraconazole (10 mg/ml) and or Fluconazole (2mg/ml).

*** Adjunctive therapy:**

- Cyclopentolate (Thilo) eye drops, 3 times/day.
- Isoptofenicol (Alcon) eye drops , 5 times /day.
- Thilotears gel (Thilo) , twice daily.
- A weak corticosteroid drops (FML from Allergan) twice daily was added if there is immune ring or associated uveitis in addition to topical and systemic non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.
- For cases not responding to treatment within the frist week; a debridment of superficial corneal layers was done to enhance good penetration of antifungal therapy.

Figure (1) Patients with Mycotic keratitis with Laboratory results

*** Analysis of the data:** -data were tabulated and analysed statistically using Chi square test at the 5 % level of significance and student T test.

Results:

A total number of 8030 patients attended the outpatient Ophthalmology Clinic of Tanta University during summer months. Our target were Fifty patients (cases) with mycotic keratitis representing 0.62% of the total attendants, while those with non mycotic keratitis accounted to 75 cases (the control group) representing 0.93 % of the total attendants of the clinic during that period .

Age & Sex:

- The mean age for cases of mycotic keratitis was 49.18 ± 2.28 years ; while mean age for the non-mycotic group was 50.88 ± 2.60 years .
- Table (2) shows that males in patients of mycotic keratitis were affected twice more than females. They were 33 males accounting for 66% and 17 females representing 34% respectively. The same was found with the control group (non mycotic keratitis), they were 72% males and 28% females. However the difference was statistically not significant between mycotic and non mycotics as regards the sex ($X^2=0.50$, $P>0.05$) .
- Fourty six percent of the cases of mycotic keratitis were at the age group (>40-60ys), the same was recorded with cases of non mycotic keratitis , they were 52% at the age group (>40-60 ys). The difference between mycotic and non mycotic keratitis was statistically not significant regarding the different age groups ($X^2= 0.46$).

Socio-demographic indicators (Table 3)

A - Occupation:

- As shown in table (3) farmers (unskilled workers) represented the majority of cases (64%) and they were more than non-mycotic keratitis (50 %); while professionals and semiprofessionals represented only 4% of the mycotic group compared to 30% among the control group. Housewives were more among cases than the control, they were 20% and 12% respectively. The difference was statistically significant between cases of mycotic and non mycotic keratitis as regards their occupations ($X^2=12.79$).

B – Family size:

- More than one third of cases of mycotic keratitis were of large family size (>6 persons) compared to the control group (36% and 12%) respectively. While the percentage of cases with small family size (≤ 4 persons) was less than the control group, they were (26% and 37.33%) respectively. The difference was statistically significant ($X^2= 10.22$) .

C- Crowding Index:

- Sixty four percent of cases with mycotic keratitis lived in overcrowded houses with crowding index >2. This was slightly more than that of non mycotic keratitis (56%) . There

Table (2) age and sex distribution among mycotic and non mycotic keratitis

Age* Sex**		Mycotic keratitis			Non mycotic K.		
		Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
-40	No	10	3	13	10	8	18
	%	30.3	17.6	26.0	18.52	38.10	24.0
>40 -60	No	16	7	23	30	9	39
	%	48.5	41.2	46.0	55.6	42.9	52
> 60	No	7	7	14	14	4	18
	%	21.2	41.2	28.0	29.93	19.05	24.0
Total	No	33	17	50	54	21	75
	%	100	100	100	100	100	100

Age, $X^2 = 0.46$, $P > 0.05$.

Sex , $X^2 = 0.50$, $P > 0.05$.

Table (3) Some socio-demographic indicators among cases of mycotic keratitis and control

Occupation	Mycotic Keratitis		Non mycotic Keratitis		Test of significance
	No	%	No	%	
Professional & semi proff.	2	4.0	22	29.33	*X ² = 12.79 # P <0.05
Skilled workers	6	12.0	6	8.0	
Unskilled workers	32	64.0	38	50.67	
House wives	10	20.0	9	12.0	
Family size					
< 4	13	26.0	28	37.33	*X ² = 10.22
>4 -6	19	38.0	38	50.67	
> 6	18	36.0	9	12.0	
Crowding index					
< 2	18	36.0	33	44.0	X ² = 0.79
>2	32	64.0	42	56.0	
Residence					
Rural	32	64.0	42	56.0	X ² = 0.79
Urban	18	36.0	33	44.0	
Water source					
Indoor	15	30.0	34	45.33	X ² = 2.96
Outdoor	35	70.0	41	54.67	
Sewage disposal					
Pipes	9	18.0	34	45.33	*X= 9.31
Conservancy system	41	82.0	41	54.67	

- X² (mycotic keratitis versus non mycotic keratitis)
- (*)P <0.05 (statistically significant)

was no significant statistical difference between mycotic and non mycotic keratitis regarding the crowding index ($X^2= 0.79$).

E -Residence:

- In cases of mycotic keratitis , 64% were rural residents compared to 56% among the control group . The difference was statistically not significant between mycotic and non mycotic groups ($X^2= 0.79$) .

F- Water source:

- Outdoor water supply represented about three quarters (70%) of the houses of mycotic cases and more than half of those in non mycotic keratitis (54%) . However, the difference was statistically not significant ($X^2=2.96$) .

G-Sewage disposal :

- In cases of mycotic keratitis only 18% of patients had pipes system of sewage disposal in their houses compared to 45.33% in the houses of non-mycotic group with a significant statistical difference ($X^2=9.31, P<0.05$) .

Time between the onset of complaints and examination:

- From table (4) and figure (2) it was found that among the mycotic group 60 % of cases came within the first week from the onset of complaints while about a quarter(22%) of cases came for ocular examination >14 days up to 30 days. In non-mycotic corneal ulcers the majority (90%) came within the first week of complaints and no one came after 14 days . The difference between the two groups was statistically significant as regards the different periods of time ($X^2=15.14$ & $P<0.05$), also there was a significant difference between means of time between both groups ($t= 4.52, p<0.05$).

Laboratory results

- Table (5) and figure (3) revealed that Aspergillus species constituted the majority of cases with positive cultures. Aspergillus flavus in 28% of cases and Aspergillus niger in 16 % and the least frequent species was Candida albicans (2 %) . Negative cultures occurred in 20 % of cases inspite of their improvement with antifungal therapy and their typical clinical findings for diagnosis.

Risk factors

Table (6) and figure (4) showed that Trauma whether organic or non organic was the most frequent risk factor for both of mycotic (52%) and non mycotic (72%) groups. Organic ocular trauma was the most frequent risk factor in mycotic keratitis(in 32% of cases) while non organic trauma was the most risky for the control group (44%). Other risk factors included ocular surgery which represented 30% of mycotic cases compared to 0 % among non mycotic group. Prolonged local antibiotics uptake was risky for 6% of mycotic keratitis compared to no one among non mycotic group . Systemic diseases represented the least frequent risk for mycotic keratitis (2% of the cases) while it was 8% in non mycotic keratitis . All cases of mycotic keratitis who had a history of ocular surgery had a mild course of corticosteroid therapy except in 8 cases who had a prolonged heavy course.

Figure (2): Time of onset of ocular

Figure (3): Types of fungal Isolates

Figure (4) Risk factors

Table (4) Onset of complaints for mycotic and non mycotic keratitis

Time	Mycotic keratitis		Non mycotic keratitis		Test of significance
	No	%	No	%	
≤ 7 days	30	60.0	67	89.33	
>7 – 14 days	9	18.0	8	10.67	*X ² = 15.14
>14- 30 days	11	22.0	0	0.0	*t= 4.52

* statistically significant, P<0.05

Table (5) Types of fungal infections among the cases

Type of fungus	Cases	
Aspergillus flavus	No	14
	%	28.0%
Aspergillus niger	No	8
	%	16.0%
Mucor racemosus	No	7
	%	14.0%
Cladosporium sphaerospermum	No	6
	%	12.0%
Penicillium Lanosum	No	4
	%	8.0%
candida albicans	No	1
	%	2.0%
negative culture	No	10
	%	20.0%
Total	No	50
	%	100.0%

Table (6) Different risk factors among cases of mycotic keratitis and control

Risk factors / Cases and control		Mycotic keratitis	non mycotic
Systemic dis.	No	1	6
	%	2.0%	8.0%
ocular surgery	No	15	0
	%	30.0%	0.0%
OcularTrauma (Organic)	NO	16	21
	%	32.0%	28.0%
Ocular trauma (non organic)	No	10	33
	%	20.0%	44.0%
Prolongged local antibiotic	No	3	0
	%	6.0%	0.0%
more than one factor	No	3	9
	%	6.0%	12.0%
No obvious causes	No	2	6
	%	4.0%	8.0%
Total	No	50	75
	%	100.0%	100.0%

Fate and complications:

- Eight patients (16%) showed complete healing, 9 patients (18%) showed healing with faint nebulae, 26 patients (52%) showed healing with dense vascularized leucoma, 3 patients with descematocele (6%), 2 patients (4%) with perforation and 2 patients (4%) ended by endophthalmitis as shown in figures (5 & 6).

Figure (5): Fate and complications

Discussion

Corneal infections including fungal types are responsible for about 50% of corneal scarring in the developing world which is a significant cause of blindness⁽¹⁴⁾. Mycotic keratitis is a growing health problem in the developing countries representing from one third up to 56% of total ocular infections⁽¹⁵⁾. World health organization reported that about 10 millions all over the world were blind due to corneal infections in its program for prevention of blindness (Global initiative vision by the year 2020)⁽¹⁵⁾.

Age and Sex:

- In the present work about half the cases of mycotic keratitis were at the age group > 40 –60 years, and males were about two times more affected than females. These findings were close to that of Chander J. and Sharma A., 1994⁽⁵⁾ in their study in India where as they concluded that fungal keratitis affected males three times more than females and were more frequent in the age group from 50 to 60 years. Other studies^(7 & 16) revealed that fungal keratitis affected males more than females and were more common in those aged >20 years up to 50 years. Males are more affected because of their more activity and movement in the surrounding environment which expose them to different risks such as corneal trauma. There were no significant statistical differences between cases of mycotic keratitis and those of non mycotic keratitis as regards the age groups and sex.

Figure (6): Fate and complications of Mycotic Keratitis

Socio-demographic indicators:

- In this study, mycotic keratitis affected farmers (unskilled workers) more than other occupations in (64%) of the cases followed by house wives in 20%. These findings were consistent with Moharram et al, in 1999⁽⁸⁾ in their study in Assuit where as 47% of cases of fungal keratitis were farmers and 20% were housewives. Farming was the main job for most of cases of fungal keratitis in other studies^(5&17&18). Most of fungal species such as *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Mucorhacimos* species and *Cladosporium* are soil fungi; so they contaminate vegetables and fruits. Farmers are usually exposed to trauma by organic matter (such as dried rice stems or maize) which facilitate invasion of the cornea by the fungi. There was a significant statistical difference between cases of fungal keratitis and the control regarding their occupations. Farmers were more recorded among cases while professionals and semi-professionals were more recorded among the control. Professionals might be exposed to some risk factors such as the non-organic trauma but rarely exposed to organic trauma which is associated mostly with fungal contamination. In this study organic trauma was the most risky factor for fungal keratitis while non organic trauma was the most risky for the control group and this might explain the former finding.
- This study reported that cases of mycotic keratitis belonged to large families (>4 persons in 38% and > 6 persons in 36%), with a high crowding index (64% of cases with crowding index >2) and about two thirds (in 64%) of them were rural. There was a significant statistical difference between cases and control as regards their family size (larger families among mycotic keratitis cases) but there were no significant statistical differences regarding both of crowding index and rural residence. However in both of mycotic and non mycotic keratitis the percentage of the disease was higher in large families, with a high crowding index and rural residence. These were explained by the unsound health behavior and lack of health awareness especially in those living in overcrowded houses with bad sanitation. These factors facilitated infections especially with morbid corneas. These findings were in agreement with other studies^(5&18&20) which reported that fungal and microbial keratitis associated with low socio-economic status and rural residence.
- As regards water sources, the outdoor water supply accounted to 70% of the houses of cases compared to 54.67% among the control with no significant statistical difference. Concerning sewage disposal, more than three quarters of houses of mycotic keratitis (82%) were by conservancy system compared to 54.67% of the houses in the control with a significant statistical difference. In conclusion, it was revealed that cases of mycotic keratitis lived in more deteriorated environment than the control group; this was consistent with VajPayee R. 1999⁽¹⁹⁾ who reported that cases of mycotic keratitis lived in poor insanitary environment. Dunlop AA., (1994)⁽²⁰⁾ reported that eye washing with contaminated water could cause mycotic and non-mycotic keratitis. Outdoor water and insanitary sewage could affect personal hygiene and self care with poor sanitation of houses together with spread of flies and insects that transmit organisms easily to healthy or unhealthy corneas.

Time of onset of complaints: In this study, 60% of cases of mycotic keratitis came within the first week of their onset of complaints to seek medical care compared to the majority in the control group. About a quarter of cases of mycotic keratitis (22%) came to seek medical care after two weeks from onset of complaints compared to no one in the control. The differences in mean time as well as the different periods of time were significant ($t= 4.52$ and $X^2= 15.14$). this might be explained by the followings; first, some patients developed mycotic keratitis after ocular surgery and thought that their complaints were a normal sequence of the surgery, so they delayed in seeking care; second, some other patients were post traumatic and thought that the symptoms were a normal

sequence of trauma. Lastly, some patients were treated by mistake at first as non-mycotic keratitis till they were managed as fungal keratitis.

As regards laboratory findings for fungal growth It was found that 80% of patients were positive, while 20% were negative inspite of their typical clinical findings and their improvement with antifungal therapy. These may be explained by some fungi present in deep stroma couldn't be obtained if superficial scraping was done or if scraping was obtained only from one area. These findings were in consistence with Chander and Sharma, 1994⁽⁵⁾ who reported that 16.39% of their patients showed negative fungal growth inspite of their typical clinical findings for fungal keratitis.

- **For the type of fungus isolated**, it was found that *Aspergillus* species were the most common (44%) either *flavus* (28%) or *niger* (16%); which was in agreement with Chander and Sharma⁽⁵⁾ in India who demonstrated that *Aspergillus* species constituted the majority (40.1%) of fungal growth in their study. Other study⁽²¹⁾ in Saudia Arabia demonstrated that *Aspergillus* species occurred in 41%. These findings may be explained by the more spread of *Aspergillus* species in the environment specially spores which can survive hot and dry weather for long time. *Aspergillus* species existed in the soil and animal skin so, they were more frequent among the farmers in this study.
- Among *Aspergillus* species it was found that *Aspergillus flavus* constituted 28% and *Aspergillus niger* 16%. This was consistent with the findings of other study⁽²²⁾ that demonstrated 17.1% *flavus* and 13.7% *niger*.
- *Candida* species were the least frequent type (only in 2%), that is in agreement with other study⁽²³⁾ which reported that *Candida* and *Fusarium* species were the least common in their study.
- Our results revealed that among a total number of 8030 cases examined during summer months, mycotic keratitis occurred among 0.62% of cases and the non mycotic in 0.93%. A study was done from Jan. 1991 to Dec. 1998 in LV Prasad eye institute demonstrated 2655 cases of infectious keratitis, they were 63.6% bacterial, 33.6% fungal and 2.7% parasitic. Among fungal cases *Aspergillus* species were responsible for 33% of cases, *Fusarium* in 35.1%, dematiaceous fungi in 14.4%, other hyaline fungi in 16.4% and *candida* only in 1%⁽¹⁴⁾.
- In Singapore a retrospective study⁽²²⁾ was done of culture- positive fungal keratitis from Jan. 1991 to Dec 1995 revealed only 29 cases and most common species was *fusarium* (52%) while *aspergillus* was (17%).
- In Sri lanka, a two years period study revealed only 66 cases of Bacterial and mycotic keratitis⁽²⁴⁾.
- In South Florida, a study⁽²⁵⁾ over 10 – years period was done revealed only 125 cases of fungal keratitis identified in the microbiology laboratory records between Jan. 1982 and Jan. 1992.
- Two years study of patients with corneal ulcers in Tribhuvan University Teaching Hospital in Kathmandu Nepal⁽²³⁾, reported that fungal ulcers occurred in 27 patients out of 405 (6.7%), While bacterial ulcers in 256 (63.2%) of patients and mixed aetiology in 41 patients (10.1%).

- This work reported that among cases of mycotic keratitis, organic trauma was the most prevalent risk factor (32%), followed by ocular surgery in 30% of cases then the non-organic trauma in 20% followed by the use of topical antibiotics in 6% and systemic disease (such as diabetes) was the least frequent in only 2%. On the other hand the non-organic trauma was the most frequent risk factor for non mycotic keratitis (in 44%) followed by the organic trauma in 28%. Farmers were more exposed to organic trauma (with rice or maize stems or others) during farming so they were more exposed to mycotic keratitis. As regards the risk of ocular surgery among the cases, fungal contamination might occur preoperative in those cases with negative cultures or postoperative due to lowered body immunity (by the stressful surgery) and or the use of a course of local and systemic corticosteroids with the surgery. In consistence with our findings, ocular trauma was the most frequent risk either for mycotic or non mycotic keratitis in other studies ^(19,22,25,26). Organic trauma was the most frequent risk factor for mycotic keratitis in other study ⁽¹⁶⁾. Panda A etal 1997 ⁽²⁷⁾ in India recorded that trauma was the most common predisposing factor in 55.3% among cases of mycotic keratitis followed by systemic illness in 11.2% and previous ocular surgery in 9.8%. ChanderJ. And Sharma A. 1994 ⁽⁵⁾ portrayed that trauma followed by the use of topical antibiotics and corticosteroids were the most common factors for mycotic keratitis.

Recommendation:

- Community awareness of the risk factors such as minor trauma and the use of contaminated traditional eye solutions. Farmers in particular and laboured workers can be educated to protect their eyes against trauma and to seek for medical consultation immediately after trauma.
- Restriction of the abuse of topical corticosteroids or antibiotics.
- Mycotic keratitis should be suspected in every patient with a corneal lesion, specially the resistant one and should be ruled out before commencing steroids and antibiotics.
- Early recognition and instillation of the appropriate therapy by community workers and ophthalmologists.
- Referral of advanced cases to eye care centers with proper management of complications
- For a successful treatment , we need:
 - A- Proper early clinical diagnosis
 - B- Proper laboratory diagnosis that helped by deep scraping of the ulcer or even biopsy .
 - C- Initiating a broad spectrum antifungal drug till laboratory findings prove the specific drug.
 - D- Proper frequency of antifungal drugs.
 - E- Proper timing for termination of therapy.

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Für Patienten

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Lehre

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Herzlich Willkommen auf den Internetseiten der Augenklinik und Poliklinik des Klinikums der Universität München

Die Augenklinik ist eine Klinik der Maximalversorgung und eine der größten Augenkliniken in Europa

Es werden Patienten in 19 Spezialambulanzen in allen Bereichen der Augenheilkunde behandelt und das gesamte Leistungsspektrum der Augenheilkunde abgebildet.

Außerhalb der regulären Öffnungszeiten besteht eine Notfallversorgung, die auch eine 24-stündige OP Bereitschaft umfasst.

Prof. Dr. med. Siegfried Priglinger

Direktor der Augenklinik

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